

Art, Flowers, and Connoisseurship under the Tokugawa Shogunate The Cultural Bond between Kanō Tan'yū and Lord Nagai Naomasa

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Introduction

Kanō Tan'yū (1602–1674), one of the most prominent painters of the Edo period, served as an official painter (*goyō eshi*) of the Tokugawa shogunate and established the refined and elegant style that came to be known as the Edo Kanō school. He is widely recognized as a leading figure in early modern Japanese painting. Tan'yū's extensive network of personal and professional connections has been the subject of scholarly attention, particularly his interactions with distinguished cultural figures of the time, including Ishin Sūden (1569–1633, abbot of Konchi-in at Nanzen-ji), Kōgetsu Sōgan (1574–1643, abbot of Daitoku-ji), Hōrin Jōshō (1593–1668, abbot of Rokuon-ji), and Sakuma Sanekatsu (1570–1642, hatamoto and tea practitioner). More recently, scholars such as Satoru Sakakibara and Mutsumi Kadowaki have revealed Tan'yū's previously unknown relationships with various daimyō, including Matsudaira Naonori (1642–1695) and Inaba Masanori (1623–1696).¹ Drawing on this rich network, Tan'yū responded not only to official commissions from the shogunate but also to requests from court nobles, temples, and shrines, producing a wide range of works from large-scale compositions to delicate handscrolls.

One of the key factors that enabled Kanō Tan'yū to maintain close ties with court nobles and cultural figures in Kyoto was his possession of residences in both Edo (Kajibashi 鍛冶橋) and Kyoto (Takatsuji 高辻).² Leveraging these dual bases of activity, Tan'yū received requests for authentication from across the provinces, recording his appraisals in annotated drawings known today as *Tan'yū shukuzu* (Tan'yū's sketches with inscriptions). Furthermore, as he traveled back and forth between Kyoto and Edo, he sketched a wide array of plants sent to him by acquaintances throughout the country, leaving behind some of the earliest extant examples of botanical sketching in early modern Japan.

Among these richly detailed sketches are the five-volume *Sketches of Flowers and Plants* (Tokyo National Museum, A-216) and the one-volume *Sketches of Flowers and Plants* included in *Tan'yū Shukuzu* (Kyoto National Museum, A 甲-242-3), which appear to have been created for private purposes. These scrolls include delicate renderings of familiar native flora, exotic imports, and newly circulated horticultural

varieties. The individuals who supplied Tan'yū with these plants are presumed to have been members of his personal circle, and as such, the names recorded in the inscriptions offer valuable insights into his private life.

In the course of investigating Tan'yū's social network through the identities of those who provided subjects for his sketches, the name "Shinsai" (信齋) emerges. During this period, the name Shinsai was used by none other than Nagai Naomasa (永井尚政, 1587–1668), a prominent daimyō and tea practitioner.³ Given that the *Tan'yū shukuzu* includes inscriptions such as "Painting by Nagai Shinsai," it is reasonable to identify the "Shinsai" mentioned in the sketch scrolls as Naomasa.

This study thus seeks to examine the previously unexplored relationship between Tan'yū and Naomasa, using both the *shukuzu* and the botanical sketch scrolls as primary sources. By shedding light on the connection between Tan'yū, the shogunate's official painter, and Naomasa, the daimyō tea master known as Shinsai, this study aims to illuminate the cultural roles both figures came to embody in their later years.

I . The Inscription "Shinsai" in *Sketches of Flowers and Plants* and Related Works

The five-volume *Sketches of Flowers and Plants* and the one-volume scroll included in the corpus known as *Tan'yū shukuzu* are compilations of observational drawings made by Kanō Tan'yū based on direct study of plant specimens. According to the date inscriptions found within the images, these drawings were produced over approximately thirteen years, from around 1661 (Manji 4/ Kanbun1) to 1674 (Enpō 2), the final years of Tan'yū's life.

The version housed in the Tokyo National Museum is organized by season into volumes titled "Spring," "Summer," "Autumn," and two volumes labeled "Miscellaneous." On the hundreds of individual sheets that comprise the scrolls, not only the date of production but also the plant names, names of those who provided the specimens, and place names are frequently recorded as inscriptions or marginal notes.

Among these annotations, the name "Shinsai" appears in connection with four specific drawings: *Sawagikyō* (*Lobelia sessilifolia*; fig. 1), *Botan* (Peony; fig. 2), *Dandoku-sō* (*Canna*; fig. 3), and *Shūkaidō* (*Begonia grandis*; fig. 4). The inscriptions associated with these works read as follows:

September 23, Kanbun 3 (1663)

Sawagikyō: When brought to Shinsai, sketched at Tōtei
(*Sketches of Flowers and Plants*, "Summer" volume)

October 8, Kanbun 3 (1663)

Botan: Came from Shinsai. A winter-blooming peony. Fully bloomed—very beautiful—crimson

(*Sketches of Flowers and Plants*, “Summer” volume)

July 19, Kanbun 5 (1665)

Dandoku-sō: Came from Shinsai

(*Sketches of Flowers and Plants*)

July 29, Kanbun 5 (1665)

Shūkaidō: Came from Shinsai

(*Sketches of Flowers and Plants*)

These inscriptions clearly indicate that Shinsai supplied the botanical specimens depicted in these drawings.

Fig. 1 Kanō Tan'yū, *Sketches of Flowers and Plants*: Summer Scroll (*Sawa-kikiyō*), Tokyo National Museum

Fig. 2 Same (*Peony*), Kanbun 3 (1663)

Fig. 3 Kanō Tan'yū, *Sketches of Flowers and Plants*, Kyoto National Museum, Kanbun 5 (1665)

Fig. 4 Same (*Autumn Chinese Bellflower*), Kanbun 5 (1665)

Nagai Naomasa took Buddhist vows in 1658 (Meireki 4) and adopted the name Shinsai. Since all four of the aforementioned botanical sketches date from the Kanbun era (1661–1673), it is clear that the plants were drawn after Naomasa's tonsure. The sketch of *Sawagikyō* (*Lobelia sessilifolia*), made at the "Tōtei" (Eastern Pavilion) in the garden of Naomasa's residence, depicts a plant native to the watersides of Japan. This species is referenced in the sixteenth-century flower arrangement manual *Ikenobō Sen'ō Kuden* as a plant "not to be arranged tall,"⁴ indicating that it was already well known by the seventeenth century.

In contrast, *Dandoku* (*Canna indica*), native to tropical America, was introduced to Japan in the early Edo period following its global dissemination after the sixteenth century. It would have still been considered a relatively novel horticultural species in the

Kanbun era. Similarly, *Shūkaidō* (*Begonia grandis*), a naturalized plant brought from China for ornamental purposes, was also a new and unfamiliar species at the time.

The fact that Naomasa provided such novel plants is entirely consistent with his well-documented enthusiasm for camellias, which had become immensely popular in the seventeenth century. The *Kakumeiki* contains multiple entries noting that Naomasa gifted various camellia cultivars to Emperor Go-Mizunoo.⁵

Furthermore, within the *Tan'yū shukuzu* (Sketches by Tan'yū) housed at the Kyoto National Museum, the *Sansui kachō zukan* (Scroll of Landscapes, Flowers, and Birds; Kyoto National Museum, A-甲-248-1) includes copies of two bird-and-flower paintings that were once in the possession of Nagai Naomasa. The inscriptions accompanying these images read as follows:

First month, 10th day, Kanbun 2 (1662)

Painting for Nagai Shinsai — Not particularly good (*amari yoku nasu sōrō*) —
[inscribed by] Untō(雲濤)

Same day

Painting by Nagai Shinsai — Appraised as Nōsai(納齋) (*nōsai to gedai kakisōrō*)
These records note that one painting titled *Untō* (Clouds and Waves) was deemed “not particularly good,” while the other was appraised as a work by Nōsai, as indicated in the inscribed title.

In contrast, within the same *Tan'yū shukuzu* corpus, the *Busson soshisen'nin kachōjū gasatsu* (Album of Buddhist Images, Patriarchs, Immortals, Birds and Flowers, and Animals; Kyoto National Museum, A-甲-278-2) includes two sketches associated with Nagai Naomasa. One is attributed to Gessai and bears an inscription identifying it as belonging to “Nagai Shinano-dono” (Lord Shinano). The other, dated to the end of Jōō 4 (1655), is accompanied by the note “Shinano-dono.” From these two examples, it can be confirmed that prior to his tonsure, Naomasa was referred to with the honorific -
dono.

The absence of any such honorific following his tonsure—when he had assumed the name Shinsai—might suggest a degree of familiarity or intimacy in his relationship with Tan'yū. However, considering that an *ingō* (cloistered title) itself carries honorific weight, this point warrants further consideration from a different perspective. Before turning to the implications of naming conventions, it is necessary to examine what kind of figure Naomasa truly was.

According to the *Kansei chōshū shokafu* (Genealogies of Retainer Families, Revised in the Kansei Era),⁶ Nagai Naomasa was born in 1587 (Tenshō 15) in Suruga Province as the eldest son of Nagai Naokatsu (1563–1626). In 1600 (Keichō 5), he joined his father in participating in the Battle of Sekigahara. In 1602 (Keichō 7), he was appointed as an personal attendant to Tokugawa Hidetada (徳川秀忠), the second shogun.

In 1605 (Keichō 10), Naomasa accompanied Hidetada on his journey to Kyoto, and in the same year, he was granted the court rank of *Shinano no Kami* (Governor of Shinano Province). He distinguished himself in both the Winter Campaign of Osaka in 1614 (Keichō 19) and the Summer Campaign of 1615 (Genna 1), and was appointed as *koshōgumi bantō* (captain of the page corps). In 1619 (Genna 5), he received a fief of 10,000 *koku* in Uruido, Kazusa Province, and in 1622 (Genna 8), he was elevated to the position of *rōjū* (senior councilor of the shogunate).

In 1623 (Genna 9), he was granted an additional 5,000 *koku* in Yamana, Tōtōmi Province, bringing his total to 24,000 *koku*. In 1626 (Kanei 3), he inherited his father's domain of 62,000 *koku*, including holdings in Koga and the Kōnosu Palace grounds in Shimōsa Province, raising his total holdings to 89,100 *koku*. Of this, he distributed 10,000 *koku* among his younger brothers, Naokiyo, Naosada, and Naochika.

Naomasa, along with Itakura Shigemune and Inoue Motonari, was one of the “Three Close Attendants” (*kinjū no sanshin*) to Shogun Tokugawa Hidetada and was held in high regard. When Hidetada abdicated and moved to the Nishi-no-maru (Western Bailey) of Edo Castle, Naomasa was appointed as *Nishi-no-maru rōshoku* (senior official of the Western Bailey). Upon receiving his late father's former domain of Koga, he continued to serve with distinction under the third shogun, Tokugawa Iemitsu (徳川家光). Notably, during the shogun's pilgrimage to Nikkō, Naomasa was entrusted with the duty of presenting meals at the temporary lodging station (*o-tsugi yado*), reflecting his continued prominence.

Naomasa was frequently appointed as *bugyō* (magistrate) in charge of major construction projects during the early Edo period. Among the most significant of these were: the construction of the stone walls at the Yamazato Entrance of Edo Castle's Nishi-no-maru in 1629 (Kanei 6); the building of the Taiyū-in Mausoleum at Zōjō-ji Temple and the Momijiyama Mausoleum at Edo Castle in 1632 (Kanei 9); the completion of the main keep (tenshukaku) of Edo Castle in 1638 (Kanei 15); and the construction of the *sukiya* (tea ceremony residence) in the Nishi-no-maru Yamazato compound in 1640 (Kanei 17).

Later, in 1653 (Jōō 2), he was appointed as the magistrate for the Imperial Palace reconstruction (*kinri zōei bugyō*), overseeing the construction of a new palace, which was completed in 1655 (Meireki 1). In recognition of his service, he was granted an imperial gift of perfumed incense and a sword, both designated as imperial commissions (*chokusaku* 勅作).

In 1633 (Kanei 10), Naomasa was granted the position of *rōjū* (senior councilor) and received a fief of 100,000 *koku* in Yodo, Yamashiro Province. From that time onward, he assumed responsibility for maintaining peace and order in Kyoto and the surrounding Kinai region, supervising key officials such as Itakura Shigemune, the *shoshidai* (Kyoto deputy), and Kobori Masakazu, the *bugyō* (magistrate) of Fushimi. In 1637 (Kanei 14), during the Shimabara Rebellion, Naomasa was entrusted with the defense of Kyoto.

From this period, during his tenure as lord of the Yodo domain, records increasingly highlight Naomasa's participation in tea gatherings. According to the *Kansei chōshū shokafu*, in 1634 (Kanei 11), when Shogun Tokugawa Iemitsu visited Yodo Castle, Naomasa performed tea service for him. Additional records indicate that he also offered tea at the Ninomaru (Second Bailey) of Edo Castle in 1636 (Kanei 13) and again in the first month of 1639 (Kanei 16), at the *sukiya* (tea pavilion) in Shinagawa in 1638 (Kanei 15), and on several occasions in 1641 (Kanei 18) at the *sukiya* in the Yamazato compound of the Nishi-no-maru (Western Bailey) of Edo Castle.⁷⁸

In the tenth month of that same year (Kanei 18), Naomasa was formally granted leave from his post by Shogun Iemitsu. On that occasion, he was presented with a gift of tea and a *bokuseki* (ink inscription) written by the Zen master Wuzhun Shifan (無準師範),⁹ signifying both imperial favor and his elevated cultural standing.

Even after assuming the position of lord of the Yodo domain—and indeed even after formally retiring from office—Nagai Naomasa was repeatedly summoned to confer with various magistrates (*bugyō*) in the Kinai region on important matters of governance. His continued engagement with the shogunate during his retirement in Kyoto suggests that he remained an influential figure in political affairs. At Yodo as well, he acted as a key cultural intermediary between the warrior class and the imperial court, representing the cultured elite among the samurai.

Naomasa studied the *chanoyu* (tea ceremony) under Furuta Oribe and later maintained close ties with Kobori Enshū, not only in official matters but also through frequent participation in tea gatherings.¹⁰ Kanō Tan'yū, for his part, had been influenced from an early age by Tsuda Sōgyū's son, Sōan, and by Shōgen, a disciple of Oribe; he,

too, was a tea associate of Enshū.¹¹ It is worth noting that, by the Kanbun era, following Enshū's death, figures such as Tan'yū and Naomasa had come to embody Edo-period cultural ideals, transcending official roles and sharing a common aesthetic sensibility and body of knowledge.

Although, to the best of my knowledge, no extant *chakai ki* (tea gathering records) indicate that Tan'yū and Naomasa attended the same tea gathering, the botanical sketch scrolls provide clear evidence of a close personal relationship between the official painter (*go-yō eshi*) and the daimyō tea practitioner. Their association appears to have been grounded not merely in shared participation in tea gatherings, but in a deeper mutual affinity for the aesthetic principles that underpinned *chanoyu* itself. In what follows, I shall examine the cultural profiles of both men as practitioners of the tea ceremony.

II. Chanoyu and the Cultural Exchange between Tan'yū and Naomasa

One of the most renowned tea containers associated with Kanō Tan'yū is the *Tanemura chaire* (種村茶入 shoulder-shaped tea caddy). During the fire of Meireki 2 (1656), which consumed Tan'yū's residence, a devoted disciple risked his life to retrieve the tea caddy from the flames. Though the disciple perished, the paulownia-wood box that held the caddy was found beside his body and was picked up by a courier, who later sold it to Tachibana-ya Sōgen, a dealer in Chinese wares in Kyoto. Suspecting that the object was a famous *meibutsu* (celebrated tea utensil) and possibly property of the shogunate, Sōgen inquired with Makino Chikanari, the Kyoto *shoshidai*. It was confirmed to be the chaire that Tan'yū had lost in the fire.

Tan'yū repurchased the chaire for the considerable sum of 300 *kan* (strings of coins), and the piece came to be known as *Miyako-gaeri* ("Returned from the Capital").⁽¹²⁾ This chaire later came into the possession of Matsudaira Fumai (1751–1818) and is now recognized as one of the great *meibutsu* among daimyō collections. It is currently preserved in the Nomura Museum (fig. 5) under the name *Tanemura katatsuki chaire*.

Another notable object associated with Tan'yū is a bronze hexagonal flower vase known as *Kodō kuchimon rokkaku hanaire* (fig. 6, also in the Nomura Museum), bearing an inscription by Tan'yū on the lid. The piece appears in the *Kobori Enshū zōchō* (Inventory of the Possessions of Kobori Enshū) as "Metal hexagonal vase with a narrow mouth" (*kane rokkaku hanaire kuchi seko*) and is believed to have been a gift from Enshū to Tan'yū. This flower vase too was later acquired by Fumai, who added a *hanakubari*—an internal device used to support floral materials—and inscribed the box

lid with the word *hanakubari* in recognition of its utility and aesthetic significance.⁽¹³⁾ Several *chashaku* (bamboo tea scoops) made by Tan'yū are also known to survive, such as those in the collection of the Ebara Hatakeyama Museum of Arts, offering glimpses into the tea practice personally cultivated by Tan'yū.

Fig. 5 Tanemura-shouldered Tea Caddy, Nomura Museum, Southern Song–Yuan dynasty, 13th–14th century

Fig. 6 Ancient Bronze Hexagonal Flower Vase with Incised Mouth Pattern, Nomura Museum, Ming dynasty, 14th–15th century

In the case of Naomasa, his name appears as the donor of flowers for a tea gathering hosted by Itakura Shigemune (板倉重宗) on the third day of the fourth month in 1649 (Keian 2).¹⁴ At this gathering, white double-petaled azaleas sent by Emperor Go-Mizunoo, along with *Chiyo no Fuji* (a poetic variety of wisteria), were arranged in a fresh-cut bamboo vase. Additionally, the two-ken-wide side alcove was adorned with a large boat-shaped container filled with Atago deutzia, as well as various vessels including sand trays, bronze vases, baskets, and wooden pails, which held peonies and a diverse array of seasonal flowers. These floral offerings had all been sent by Naomasa.

The gathering also featured five varieties of tea selected for the shogun's personal tasting. Shigemune remarked, "Flowers from His Majesty the Retired Emperor, teas selected for the shogun, and auxiliary arrangements provided by Lord Shinano, that is, Nagai Naomasa —such a display would be unparalleled even in Kyoto or Nara." In response, Matsuya Hisashige is recorded to have replied with respectful admiration, saying, "An honor beyond measure." This record refers to the tea gathering hosted by Shigemune, who had once been entrusted with mediating between the court and the

shogunate during the politically sensitive period surrounding the imperial marriage of Tokugawa Masako (later Empress Masako) to Emperor Go-Mizunoo. It is particularly noteworthy that Naomasa, himself one of the “Three Close Attendants” to Shogun Hidetada, contributed such thoughtful floral arrangements. Through this episode, we catch a glimpse of Naomasa as a refined courtier deeply devoted to the appreciation of flowers.

According to the *Matsuya chakai ki* (『松屋茶会記』), the record for February 21, 1634 (Kanei 11), documents a tea gathering hosted by Naomasa himself; however, no details concerning the utensils used on that occasion are provided.¹⁵ Beyond the iron kettle named *Nosuji* (野筋), which was presented by Naomasa and preserved among the *Ryūei gomotsu* (tea utensils belonging to the Tokugawa shogunate), very little is known about the character of his tea practice.

From the *Kansei chōshū shokafu*, we learn only a few fragmentary details: that the family owned a *Bunrin* tea caddy; that Naomasa was granted a *Ruson* (Luzon) tea jar by Shogun Tokugawa Iemitsu; and that his son, Nao-yuki (尚征), inherited a self-inscribed painting by Ikkyū Sōjun (一休宗純). These brief records suggest that Naomasa’s approach to *chanoyu* may have been one of restraint, in keeping with the comportment expected of a warrior, avoiding overt displays of wealth or the pursuit of famous objects.

Even so, in the early Edo period, Naomasa’s role as a figure closely connected to both the shogunate and the imperial court—as well as his personal ties to both Furuta Oribe and Kobori Enshū—places him among the most culturally significant tea practitioners of his time.

According to the *Kobori Enshū chakai ki* (『小堀遠州茶会記』), the name of Kanō Tan’yū appears five times, while that of Nagai Naomasa is recorded on fifteen occasions.¹⁶ However, there is no indication that the two ever attended the same gathering. Similarly, in the *Eitai nikki* of Inaba Masanori (稲葉正則)—a close acquaintance of Tan’yū—there are entries noting that Naomasa and his younger brother Naokiyo (直清) were invited to tea gatherings, and that Masanori himself visited Tan’yū’s residence for a tea event. Nevertheless, no record has yet been found indicating that Tan’yū and Naomasa were present together at any such occasion.¹⁷

Despite this lack of documentation regarding shared tea gatherings, the professional connection between Tan’yū and Naomasa within official shogunal contexts is well established. As previously mentioned, during Naomasa’s tenure as construction magistrate for the Taiyū-in Mausoleum in 1632 (Kanei 9) and later for the rebuilding of the imperial palace in 1653 (Jōō 2), members of the Kanō school, under Tan’yū’s

direction, were commissioned to produce the interior wall and ceiling paintings for these official shogunal projects.

In addition, Toshie Kihara has identified several paintings by Tan'yū that were donated by Naomasa to Kōshōji Temple in Uji.¹⁸ Furthermore, Tanaka Toshio has suggested a painting of the deity Tenjin, attributed to Tan'yū and preserved at Sata Tenmangū Shrine in Osaka, which was likewise a donation by Naomasa.¹⁹

Taken together—the botanical sketch scrolls, the annotated appraisals (*shukuzu*), and several extant works by Tan'yū that were donated by Naomasa—it becomes evident that the two men shared a close and sustained personal relationship. As connoisseurs of both flora and tea utensils, and as practitioners of *chanoyu* who cultivated a refined aesthetic sensibility, the Great Fire of Meireki (1657)—which devastated the city of Edo and destroyed countless treasures, including numerous *Ryuei gomotsu* (shogunal art objects)—must have been nothing short of a nightmare for them both.

III. Appraisals of Art Objects in the Aftermath of the Great Fire of Meireki

On the eighteenth day of the first month of Meireki 3 (1657), a fire broke out at Honmyō-ji Temple in Maruyama-chō, Hongō. Driven by strong northwesterly winds, the flames swept southward from Hongō toward Tsukudajima and Ishikawajima. Fanned by westerly winds, the fire spread west from Surugadai, engulfing Denma-chō, Asakusa Gate, and Yanagibashi, ultimately jumping the Sumida River and reaching Ushijima Shinden on the eastern bank. On the following day, the nineteenth, another fire started in Shin-Takashōmachi. Also driven by northwesterly winds, this blaze consumed large swaths of Koishikawa and Iida-chō, devastating the residences of daimyō and hatamoto located to the north of Edo Castle. Eventually, the fire breached the castle grounds, destroying both the Honmaru (Main Compound) and Ninomaru (Second Compound). Flames also consumed the southeastern daimyō estates within the castle precincts and, propelled by westerly winds, reached as far as Yashōgashi, Nakabashi, Kyōbashi, Kobikichō, Teppōzu, and Shinbashi.

Later that same day, yet another fire erupted in Kōjimachi, which spread rapidly and devastated the areas around Sakuradamon Gate, Atagoshita, Shiba, and Zōjō-ji Temple. According to some accounts, the Great Fire of Meireki destroyed as much as sixty percent of the city of Edo over the course of just two days, and is said to have claimed the lives of more than 100,000 people.²⁰

Regarding the destruction of Edo Castle, the *Tokugawa jikki* records the following vivid account:

“The fierce north wind drove black smoke into the air. When the main compound seemed already on the verge of catching fire, the copper shutter on the northwest side of the second level of the keep swung open, allowing flames to pour inside. The tenshu [main tower] thus became the first to ignite. ... Over the course of the two-day blaze, the main castle compound, the second and third compounds, and more than 500 residences of daimyō and high-ranking retainers were consumed by fire.”²¹

The destruction of not only the Ninomaru and Sannomaru compounds but also the Honmaru of Edo Castle during the Great Fire of Meireki resulted in the loss of a substantial portion of the *gyobutsu*—art objects and implements owned by the Tokugawa shogunate—including tea utensils and swords. One document that sheds light on the extent of this loss is the *Meireki taika shōshitsu chadōgu mokuroku* (Inventory of Tea Utensils Lost in the Great Fire of Meireki), preserved in the Aoyama Historical Village in Sasayama and transmitted through the Aoyama family, former lords of the Sasayama domain.²² A close examination of records related to the Tokugawa family’s art collections before and after the fire suggests that many objects were either destroyed or removed from the official shogunal collection.²³ For the bakufu, the reconstruction of the *gyobutsu* collection in the aftermath of the fire must have posed a considerable challenge.

It is worth noting that among the tea-related manuscripts handed down in the Aoyama family archives, five volumes and two scrolls are explicitly marked as copies made in 1668 (Kanbun 8), on loan from Nagai Naomasa.²⁴ As Hidetaka Tanaka has aptly described, the paulownia-wood box housing the Aoyama tea manuscripts functions as a “time capsule that reveals the reception of tea texts.”²⁵ The texts copied by Aoyama Munetoshi (1604–1679) from volumes once owned by Naomasa provide valuable insight into the ownership and circulation of tea utensils in the early Edo period. These documents must have served as crucial references in the bakufu’s efforts to reconstruct its collection of tea-related objects following the fire.

While there is no direct evidence linking Naomasa to the *Inventory of Tea Utensils Lost in the Great Fire of Meireki*, it is noteworthy that Munetoshi’s cousin Yukitoshi was charged with conducting inspections in Edo following the fire, and that Naomasa’s grandson, Naonaga, married Munetoshi’s daughter. These familial ties suggest that the Aoyama and Nagai families likely shared information regarding the lost contents of the shogunal collection.

Kanō Tan'yū's residence in Kajibashi had already been destroyed in a separate fire the year prior, in 1656 (Meireki 2), during which he reportedly lost all of his old paintings and model books. The near-total absence of dates prior to the Meireki fire in Tan'yū's extant sketchbooks further supports this account. In the wake of the disaster, Tan'yū is thought to have undertaken intensive efforts to recover what had been lost by conducting numerous appraisals and producing highly detailed copies known as *shukuzu*. These appraisals and reproductions form the body of work now known as the *Tan'yū shukuzu*, a corpus that remains remarkably extensive despite later dispersal. Each *shukuzu* typically records the date of appraisal, the name of the owner, the name of the person who brought the work in, and Tan'yū's judgment concerning its authenticity and attribution. Many of the entries include the phrase *gedai tsukawashisōrō* ("title label provided"), indicating that Tan'yū likely received compensation for his services. In certain cases, when a particularly fine work was brought in, he appears to have produced full-scale reproductions of the original. One such example is the *Loquat Painting (Biwa-zu)*, now in the collection of the Freer Gallery of Art (fig. 7).

Fig. 7 Kanō Tan'yū, *Loquat*, Freer Gallery of Art, 17th century

The Loquat Painting (*Biwa-zu*) depicts a single branch of loquat with folded leaves positioned centrally on the composition. Rendered in a delicate and refined palette, it is a subtle polychrome painting of elegant simplicity. There is no inscription or poetic colophon; instead, a red seal in the shape of a gourd bearing the characters "Morinobu" (Tan'yū's art name) is affixed. From evidence found in the *Tan'yū shukuzu*, it is clear that this work is a copy by Tan'yū of a painting attributed to Sunju (Shun-kyo), also known as Qian Xuan.

In one entry of the *Tan'yū shukuzu* (Tokyo National Museum, A-9961; fig. 8), the original Loquat Painting corresponding to the Freer Gallery piece is recorded as having been brought to Tan'yū on behalf of Matsudaira Den'emon. The inscription states "Arrived from Matsudaira Den'emon," along with notes reading "Outer title indicates Sunju," and "Valuation: 500 kan," indicating that Tan'yū identified the work as by

Fig. 8 Kanō Tan'yū, *Tan'yū Shukuzu*, Tokyo National Museum, Kanbun 8 (1668)

indicating that Tan'yū identified the work as by Qian Xuan and appraised it at 500 kan. Another note reads “Wishes to possess; title label to be provided later;” suggesting that Tan'yū expressed a desire to acquire the work himself.

While copies of famous paintings were likely made even before the Great Fire, it seems that in the aftermath of the disaster, Tan'yū sought to mourn the loss of masterpieces by acquiring exceptional works that came before him during appraisals, occasionally producing meticulous reproductions. It may be inferred that preserving detailed records of these celebrated paintings for posterity became a new and vital mission for Tan'yū.

Conclusion

This study began with the inscriptions bearing the name “Shinsai” found in Kanō Tan'yū's botanical sketch scrolls and, through these records of floral exchanges, has

sought to shed light on the relationship between Tan'yū, the official painter serving the Tokugawa shogunate, and Nagai Naomasa, the daimyō tea practitioner. It has become clear that the warm personal exchanges of flowers between Tan'yū and Naomasa were preceded by professional interactions involving the commissioning and execution of official paintings, as well as requests for appraisals, all of which fostered a deeper connection between them.

Of particular interest is the fact that both men were engaged in the appraisal of celebrated paintings and renowned tea utensils in the aftermath of the Great Fire of Meireki, revealing a shared aspect of their roles as connoisseurs. This fact suggests a perspective on how the vast corpus of the *Tan'yū shukuzu*—an unparalleled body of records of appraisals and attributions in Japanese history—should be situated within the cultural and historical circumstances of the time.

Tan'yū and Naomasa each possessed exceptional discernment and refined aesthetic sensibilities. Having experienced firsthand the devastation of the Great Fire, they faced the urgent task of helping to rebuild the cultural fabric of Edo. Accordingly, their appraisals and meticulous records of the surviving masterpieces were simultaneously acts of mourning for the lost cultural treasures and endeavors to clarify the contours of what had vanished.

The few surviving botanical sketches and annotated copies of classical paintings eloquently convey the shared consciousness of beauty held by these two men of different social standing. It may well be that what they pursued together was not merely the act of appraisal itself, but a practical and heartfelt effort to mourn the lost masterpieces and to contribute to their symbolic restoration.

Notes

1. Satoru Sakakibara, *Kanō Tan'yū Goyōeshi no shōzō (Kanō Tan'yū: Portrait of an Official Painter)*, Rinsen Shoten, 2014; Mutsumi Kadowaki, *The Birth of the Master Kanō Tan'yū*, Asahi Shimbun Publications, 2014.
2. Jikansai Kobayashi, “Genealogies of the Five Branches of the Kanō Family (『狩野家五家譜』),” in *Nihon Shogaen* (Kokusho Kankōkai, 1914); Kyūho Noda, *Kanō Tan'yū*, Taitō Shoin, 1930, p. 66. See also Sakakibara, op. cit., pp. 470–486; Kadowaki, op. cit., pp. 236–242.
3. Mayumi Ono, “Kanō Tan'yū's *Scroll of Sketches of Flowers and Plants*: Chronological Trends in the Sketches and the Providers of the Subjects,” *MUSEUM*, no. 657 (2015); Nobuko Fukaya, *Nagai Naomasa: A Shogunate Senior Official Well-Versed in Aesthetics*, Miyaobi Publishing, 2017.

4. *Ikenobō Senkō Kuden* 『池坊専応口伝』, in *Kadō Kosyo Syūsei*, ed. Kadō Gaku Kenkyūkai, Dai Nippon Kadōkai, 1930.
5. *Kakumeiki* by Hōrin Jōshō, entry for March 4, Kan'ei 20 (1643), records:
“From the Imperial Retired Palace, a single camellia flower was granted for inspection. It was announced that this camellia had been presented by Nagai Shinano-no-kami. The camellia, called *Koshimino Tsubaki*, had layers of white variegation—truly a rare specimen.”
Furthermore, the entry for March 10, Shōhō 2 (1645), states:
“Ten camellia flowers were granted for inspection from the Imperial Retired Palace. It was announced that they were presented by Nagai Shinano-no-kami. The varieties included: *Shishi Tsubaki*, *Sōen Koshimino*, *Koshimino*, *Ōshiratama*, *Hitoeboshi*, *Yaejishi*, *Awamori Tsubaki*, *Sanemori*, *Ōmura*, and *Hitoejishi*—these ten kinds surprised all who saw them.” (In *Kakumeiki*, vol. 1, ed. Toshihide Akamatsu, Rokuonji, 1958).
6. See *Kansei Chōshū Shokeifu* (『寛政重修諸家譜』), vol. 10, Zoku Gunsho Ruijū Kanseikai, 1965.
7. *Tokugawa Jikki* (『徳川実紀』), entry for January 16, Kan'ei 16 (1639) (see *Tokugawa Jikki*, vol. 3, Yoshikawa Kōbunkan, 1975).
8. As noted in *Tokugawa Jikki* (op. cit.), there are no entries for February and April of Kan'ei 18 (1641), but on March 1, June 28, and August 28 it records: “Nagai Shinano-no-kami Naomasa presented tea.”
9. *Records of Items and Treasures Presented by Various Families* (『諸家遺物得物献上記』), held by the National Archives of Japan (former Shoheizaka Gakumonjo version), entry for March 6, Manji 1 (1658).
10. Osamu Mori and Kazukuni Tsunenari, *Kobori Enshū*, Sōgensha, 1974, p. 46; Isao Kumakura, *Kobori Enshū's Circle of Tea Friends*, Chuokoron-Shinsha, 2007 (originally titled *Kobori Enshū and His Tea Companions*, Taikō Shobō, 1987), pp. 232–237.
11. Nyorai Seki, “Record of the Title ‘Tanyu-sai’ by Priest Getsu,” *Touei*, no. 13 (1937); Motoaki Kono, *Nihonnobijyutsu No. 194: Kanō Tan'yū*, Shibundō, 1982; Toshie Kibara, *The search for profound delicacy : the art of Kanō Tan'yū*, Osaka University Press, 1998; Mutsumi Kadowaki, Kaneibunka no Shōzōga (*Portraits of Kan'ei Culture*), Bensei Publishing, 2003. See also Sakakibara, op. cit., pp. 354–364; Kadowaki, op. cit., pp. 144–173.
12. Kenzō Koga, “Kanō Tan'yū no cha” *Nihon Bijyutsu Kōgei*, no. 574 (1986), pp. 64–65; *Kobori Enshū's no chakai*, ed. Nezu Museum, 1996; and Kadowaki, op. cit., pp. 187–192. See also Kyūho Noda, “The Chaire of Miyakogaeri and the Nine Dragons Screen,” *Touei*,

- nos. 13–14 (1937); Yoshio Takahashi, ed., *Taishō Meikikan*, vol. 1, Shinbi Shoin, 1921, pp. 49–53.
13. See Koga, op. cit., pp. 64–65; Nezu Museum, op. cit., p. 158.
 14. Fukutarō Nagashima, ed., *Matsuya Kaiki / Hisashige Chakaiki*, in *Sadō Koten Zenshū*, vol. 9, 1957, pp. 447–449.
 15. *Ibid.*, p. 292.
 16. Sōkei Kobori, ed., *Collected Records of Kobori Enshū's Tea Gatherings* (『小堀遠州茶会記集成』), Shufunotomo, 1996; Saara Satō, “Guests Invited to Enshū's Tea Gatherings” (in Nezu Museum, op. cit., see note 9).
 17. *Yamashiro no kuni Yodo Inaba Kachū Monjyo (Documents of the Inaba Family of Yodo, Yamashiro Province); Index of Contents: Inaba Family Perpetual Diary, Inaba Shrine, Fushimi-ku, Kyoto*, ed. Odawara City History Compilation Office, 1995; see also Kadowaki, op. cit., pp. 135–144; Ono, op. cit., pp. 54–56.
 18. Kihara, op. cit., pp. 131–137.
 19. Toshio Tanaka, “Kanō Tan'yū and Kawachi Province,” *Geijyutsu*, vol. 17, Osaka University of Arts, 1994, pp. 36–39; *Survey of Oriental Art* (『東洋美術大観』), vol. 5, Shinbi Shoin, 1912, p. 363.
 20. *Tokugawa Jikki*, vol. 13, entry for January 18, Meireki 3 (1657) (see *Shintei Zōho Tokugawa Jikki*, ed. Kokushi Taikei Henshūkai, Yoshikawa Kōbunkan, 1976), and *Record of the Great Meireki Fire (Meireki Taika-ki* 『明暦大火記』, held by the National Archives of Japan). See *Tokugawa Jikki*, op. cit.
 21. *Classified Catalog of Japanese and Chinese Books in the Aoyama Collection* (『青山会文庫所蔵 和漢書分類目録』), ed. Aoyama Foundation, 1994, pp. 150–153.
 22. Hidetaka Tanaka, “Tea Texts in the Aoyama Collection,” in *Chadō Taikei*, vol. 10, ed. Hirokazu Tsutsui, supervised by Sōshitsu Sen, Tankōsha, 2001.
 23. *Ibid.*, p. 338.
 24. Tamaki Yano, *Kundaikansōtyōki no Sōgōkenkyū; Chakakō no Genten Edosyoki Ryūeigomotsu no kettei*, Bensei Publishing, 1999, pp. 245–246.

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Sources of Illustrations

Fig. 1 Kanō Tan’yū, *Sketches of Flowers and Plants: Summer Scroll (Sawa-kikiyō)*, Tokyo National Museum, <https://webarchives.tnm.jp/imgsearch/show/E0046887>.

Fig. 2 Kanō Tan’yū, *Sketches of Flowers and Plants: Summer Scroll (Sawa-kikiyō)*, Tokyo National Museum, <https://webarchives.tnm.jp/imgsearch/show/E0046899>.

Fig. 3 Kanō Tan’yū, *Sketches of Flowers and Plants*, Kyoto National Museum, https://knmdb.kyohaku.go.jp/view_16404.html. Reproduced from Mayumi Ono, “Kanō Tan’yū and Nagai Shinsai Naomasa: Acquaintance between an Appointed Painter and a Daimyo-lord Tea Master,” *MUSEUM*, no. 672 (2018).

Fig. 4 Kanō Tan’yū, *Sketches of Flowers and Plants*, Kyoto National Museum, https://knmdb.kyohaku.go.jp/view_16404.html. Reproduced from Mayumi Ono, “Kanō Tan’yū and Nagai Shinsai Naomasa: Acquaintance between an Appointed Painter and a Daimyo-lord Tea Master,” *MUSEUM*, no. 672 (2018).

Fig. 5 Tanemura-shouldered Tea Caddy, Nomura Museum, Southern Song–Yuan dynasty, 13th–14th century. Reproduced from Mayumi Ono, “Kanō Tan’yū and Nagai Shinsai Naomasa: Acquaintance between an Appointed Painter and a Daimyo-lord Tea Master,” *MUSEUM*, no. 672 (2018).

Fig. 6 Ancient Bronze Hexagonal Flower Vase with Incised Mouth Pattern, Nomura Museum, Ming dynasty, 14th–15th century. Reproduced from Mayumi Ono, “Kanō Tan’yū and Nagai Shinsai Naomasa: Acquaintance between an Appointed Painter and a Daimyo-lord Tea Master,” *MUSEUM*, no. 672 (2018).

Fig. 7 Kanō Tan’yū, *Loquat*, Freer Gallery of Art, Edo period, 17th century, https://asia.si.edu/explore-art-culture/collections/search/edanmdm:fsg_F1904.122/.

Fig. 8 Kanō Tan’yū, *Tan’yū Shukuzu (Abbreviated Sketch)*, Tokyo National Museum, 17th century, <https://webarchives.tnm.jp/imgsearch/show/E0044657>.

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